

MODERN IN TRANSPORTATION OF PASSENGERS LEARN EXPERIENCES

¹Sakhtarov Xolahmad Abduholiq ugli,

²Sakhtarov Diyorbek Abduholiq ugli

^{1,2}Students of Fergana Polytechnic Institute

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7793718>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 22th March 2023

Accepted: 30th March 2023

Online: 31th March 2023

KEY WORDS

Transport systems, public transport, sustainable development, modeling, transport model, transport, population.

ABSTRACT

Today, the main task of transport is the national economy and population timely, high-quality and complete satisfaction of the need for transport, his work is to increase economic efficiency. Transport needs of the population An important place in satisfaction is the car, which is the most massive type of passenger transport given to transport. Its technique in the development of passenger motor transport great attention should be paid to equipment and improvement of working methods. That's it At the same time, the main task is to fulfill the transportation needs of the country's population is to satisfy. Quantitative and qualitative indicators of rolling stock work does not correspond to technical and economic possibilities. More of the transport organization requires advanced forms. In the operation of passenger vehicles deficiencies reduce the quality of services to the population and rolling stock does not create conditions for effective use. Development of automobile transport with not only passenger car transport companies, but also the entire country's transport the number of tasks facing the system is also increasing. Currently in cities and villages improving the organization of the work of passenger motor transport in places, buses it is necessary to increase the regularity and speed; improving the quality of transport services to the population, technical and operational indicators of works and rolling stock develops measures to increase the efficiency of use and reduce the cost of transportation, all types of passenger transportation provides development.

High rates of urbanization, social, scientific and technical of cities development, creation of new urban planning systems, new in all areas significant transport service systems combined with the introduction of technologies determines the level of development in

advance. These systems are urban agglomerations ensuring the vitality and efficiency of the activity, all of the population's life should create an opportunity to unify the territorial dispute in the fields. External highway, local, city for goods and passenger service the only one of the big city, which consists of the surrounding and urban transport complex In the transport system, the urban passenger transport system has a separate functional place occupies Currently, the processes taking place in the work of this system are of Uzbekistan are similar in different cities and are represented by similar problems of an economic, social, normative-legal, organizational-technical, ecological nature. Theirs Most of the solutions are to increase the efficiency and quality of transport market formation of traditional forms and approaches of the management system stage requires reconsideration. Objectively passenger transport existing problems of organization and management of activities to the following criteria can be divided more conditionally.

- Problems of forming a rational transport structure, i.e. carried out in the existing market conditions between competing enterprises or modes of transport redistribution of the increased transport volume is acceptable for consumers;
- its appearance is related to the objective development process of the urban metropolis
- problems of developing new markets, both topographically and as a result of increased transport mobility of the population;
- a sufficiently large number of small enterprises operating in the market and problems of ensuring the safety of transport in the conditions of entrepreneurs, transport on compliance with the necessary requirements for organization and implementation performs independent control. Here the heterogeneous composition of the car flow and that the speed of car accidents increases in conditions of unevenness of its concentration can be distinguished;
- problems related to the social aspect of the city significant impact on the standard of living of some categories of city residents showing transport;

In terms of motor vehicle transport rates and environmental pollution related to urban planning features, land use policies, and environmental conditions group of problems. Management of urban transport in the framework of macrologistics based on the following types of management systems generally recognized in the economy can be formed: administrative - planned; market; regulated - market. First type based on strict centralization of management and state form of ownership characterized by Economic "before reconstruction" of urban passenger transport The mechanism of passenger transport volume planning and enterprises was based on the principles of planned futility. Transport yourself transfer to financing, the next on the introduction of the calculated tariff system steps changed the form, not the basic content, of the economic mechanism. It is known that the demand for transport under the conditions of the planned management system expressed in the volume of transport services provided to passengers, consumer cannot interest producers in increasing the volume and quality of services and tariffs cannot regulate a certain level of quality, uniform tariff policy and there is a fixed amount of subsidies. (subsidies). So transport The main indicators of service activity are internal production enterprises determined by the conditions.

Market system to the work of producers of various forms of ownership minimal interference by the state (mainly its role is legislation will be lowered to the level) provides. of services for this system competitiveness, free pricing, guaranteed free access to the market, supply and demand Regulation by the market is the main condition. It is the most common in the world the third intermediate type of control system. Planned and market advantages as a synthesis, it rationally combines the features of both systems provides.

Car passenger transport is the only transport system of the country is an integral part. Transport system means technological, technical and informational, legal and communication routes combined with the system of economic relations, transport means a set of tools, technical tools, management and communication tools.

The transport system is rail, sea, air, road and gas pipelines and transport combines types. Communication routes - highways, tracks, pipelines, structures, fittings and equipment for moving substations.

Means of transport - substations, pipes, containers, pallets, returnable and disposable containers.

Technical means and mechanisms - PRS, bunkers, conveyors, sorting cars. Management and communication tools - data collection, storage, processing a set of devices that provide operation and transmission. Arrange the types of transport

- stations, railway stations, airports, marinas, parking lots, service stations. The unity of the transport system is achieved by: transport, as well as throughput of processing systems;

- unity of technology, transport schedules, senders and receivers combination of agents and technological interaction provided by others field;
- information sphere of mutual cooperation;
- legal sphere of mutual relations;
- the economic sphere of interaction - based on the types of transport distribution is made up of a single planning system

Each type of transport is separate in terms of importance and scale of the national economy is a network and is considered as a complex dynamic system. A variety of public transportation the level of meeting the need for transport with types depends on a number of factors, in particular, the development of the material and technical base of a certain type of transport nature and level, the organization of the transportation process, transport depends on the regularity, reliability of delivery time. Passenger each type of transport determines and corresponds to its use has specific characteristics.

Effective operation of the passenger car transport system is all its components parts - rolling stock, motor vehicles, service development release base, communication and control technical means, transport and transport processes are achieved in the conditions of mutually coordinated development. Car passenger transport is the main form of transport for short and medium-distance travel is considered The work of passenger transport is defined as follows: transported number of passengers - volume of transport. Passenger transportation distance - travel distance, level and level of transport service. Traffic volume, taking into account their transportation distances taking transport work - the passenger turnover of this type of transport defines. The level of transport service with the level of meeting transport

needs is described. The quality of service to passengers depends on the time they travel, depending on the comfort and convenience provided to the passengers.

References:

1. Sahtarov, X. A. O., & Fayzullayev, X. (2022). Alternativ yoqilg'ilarda ishlaydigan avtomobil konstruksiyalari tahlili. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(4), 1080-1087.
2. Sakhtarov, X. A. U., & Sakhtarov, D. A. U. (2022). Remote vehicle diagnostic methods and their significance. *Science and Education*, 3(12), 385-387.
3. Ikromov, I. A., Abduraximov, A. A., & Fayzullayev, H. (2021). Experience and prospects for the development of car service in the field of car maintenance. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 11(103), 344-346.
4. Qobulov, M., Ismadiyorov, A., & Fayzullayev, X. (2022). Overcoming the Shortcomings Arising in the Process of Adapting Cars to the Compressed Gas. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 6, 109-113.
5. Qobulov, M., Ismadiyorov, A., & Fayzullayev, X. (2022). Analysis of the braking properties of the man cla 16.220 for severe operating conditions. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(03), 52-59.
6. Fayzullayev, X. (2022). Vehicle Motion Model with Wheel Lock. *Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 10, 68-73.
7. Ismadiyorov, A. A., & Sotvoldiyev, O. U. (2021). Model of assessment of fuel consumption in car operation in city conditions. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(11), 1013-1019.
8. Ismadiyorov, A. A., & Sotvoldiyev, O. U. (2021). Model of assessment of fuel consumption in car operation in city conditions. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(11), 1013-1019.
9. Abdukhalilovich, I. I., & Abdujalilovich, J. A. (2020). Description Of Vehicle Operating Conditions And Their Impact On The Technical Condition Of Vehicles. *The American Journal of Applied sciences*, 2(10), 37-40.
10. Abdujalilovich, A. J. (2022). Analysis of road accidents involving children that occurred in fergana region. *Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal*, 3(09), 57-62.
11. Axunov, J. A. (2022). Analysis of young pedestrian speed. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(4), 1-3.
12. Abdujalilovich, A. J. (2022). Analysis of the speed of children of the 46th kindergarten on margilanskaya street. *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 5, 9-11.
13. Axunov, J. A. (2022). Ta'lim muassasalari joylashgan ko 'chalarda bolalarning harakat miqdorini o 'zgarishi. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(4), 525-529.
14. Axunov, J. A. (2021). Piyodani urib yuborish bilan bog'liq ythlarni tadqiq qilishni takomillashtirish. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(11), 1020-1026.
15. Choriyev, X., & Axunov, J. (2022). Шаҳар йўловчи автомобиль транспорти тизимининг хизмат кўрсатиш сифатини таъминлаш жараёнининг функционал моделини ишлаб чиқиш (тошшаҳартрансхизмат аж таркибидаги автобус йўналишлари мисолида). *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(1), 440-453.

16. Fayziyev, P. R., Ikromov, I. A., Abduraximov, A. A., & Dehqonov, Q. M. (2022). Timeline: History of the Electric Car, Trends and the Future Developments. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 6, 89-94.
17. Fayziyev, P. R., Ikromov, I. A., Abduraximov, A. A., & Dehqonov, Q. M. (2022). Organization of technological processes for maintenance and repair of electric vehicles. *International Journal of Advance Scientific Research*, 2(03), 37-41.
18. Fayziyev, P. R., Ikromov, I. A., Otaboyev, N. I., & Abduraximov, A. A. (2022). The analysis of gas balloon supply systems. *Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 4, 115-122.
19. С.М.Ходжаев, М.С.Низомиддинова, Ч.О.Камбарова, & Н.С.Ходжаева (2022). Организация станции технического обслуживания при Ферганском политехническом институте. *Science and Education*, 3 (10), 265-274.
20. Khodjaev, S. M. (2022). THE MAIN PROBLEMS OF ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT OF CAR MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR STATIONS IN THE FERGHANA REGION. *Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal*, 3(09), 38-47.
21. Abduraxmonov, A. G., Xodjayev, S. M., Otaboyev, N. I., & Abduraximov, A. A. (2022). Formation of products from powdered polymers by rotational and blowing method. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(03), 41-51.
22. Khodjaev, S. M., & Rakhmonova, S. S. (2022). Saving resources in the operation, maintenance of automotive equipment. *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 5, 18-27.
23. Axunov, J., & Tojiboyev, S. (2023). LOGISTIKA ORQALI MAHSULOTLARNI YETKAZIB BERISH TIZIMINI BOSHQARISH. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar*, 1(7).